

PROBLEMS OF THE PROCESS, THE EFFECT OF THE INTENSITY AND TIME OF THE EFFECT OF MIXING REAGENTS WITH WATER

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Annotation. The article presents the research results and provides information on the types of reagents, types of mechanical mixers and the main tasks of the process of mixing natural turbid waters with reagents.

Key words: reagent, coagulant, mixing, perikinetetic, optokinetic, clarification and discoloration.

Introduction. One of the important steps in water quality improvement technology is the mixing of reagents with the mass of treated water. The process must satisfy two basic requirements: uniform distribution of the reagent in the volume of treated water and rapid completion of the operation. Poor performance of hydraulic mixers, in particular uneven distribution of reagents, no possibility to change the mixing regime adequate quality of treated water and type of reagent, The large volume of existing water treatment plants requires further improvement.

Methods and materials. The need to meet the first requirement can be illustrated by the example of a coagulation curve shown in the figure. 1. Suppose that there is an uneven distribution of coagulant in the mass of treated water. In the part of the water where there is a lack of coagulant (first zone to the point of fracture), the coagulation process is slow. The effect of water retention or filtration on lighting and bleaching is negligible. In the second zone, increasing the dose of coagulant is sharply on the effect of lightening and bleaching of water. The boundary between the first and second zones is called the coagulation threshold. In the third zone, increasing the dose of coagulant does not give a noticeable improvement in the brightening and bleaching effect of water. The curve is almost parallel to the axis of the abscissa. The boundary between the second and third zones is called the optimal dose and only there the process of coagulating water impurities will proceed normally. Hence the need for a uniform distribution of the reagent in the mass of treated water becomes obvious, because only then can the desired result be achieved. The process of coagulation of water impurities in time is divided into two stages: pericinetetic and orthokinetic. The process of pericinetetic coagulation occurs almost instantly, after the introduction of a coagulant into the treated water.

The aggregate stability of impurities is disrupted by the exchange adsorption of the cations of the diffuse layer of mycelium and aluminium (or iron) cations, and formation of primary aggregates. The next step is an orthokinetic coagulation process characterized by agglomeration of primary aggregates and individual impurities, which ends with the formation of large flakes visible to the armed eye.

Rice.1. The Coagulating Curve.

1- coagulation dose is insufficient; 2- increasing the dose of reagent improves the coagulation process; 3 - the dose of coagulant is excessive, loose flakes are formed; a - coagulation threshold; b is the optimal dose of coagulant.

The second step of the water coagulation process is much longer than the first. It lasts from 6-8 minutes to 1 hours and more depending on the quality of treated water (1).

It is thus obvious that the requirement for rapid and complete mixing of reagents with water arises from the need to prevent the destruction of the resulting flakes in the turbulent flow, which takes place in mixers and mixing devices. Therefore, the mixing of coagulant with water must be carried out extremely quickly, so the process that occurs in the mixer is crucial for the subsequent stages of water treatment. The importance of the instantaneous coagulant distribution process in water is explained by coagulation theory, according to which the role of intermediate dissolved aluminium complexes in destabilizing suspended particles is very large. The required speed of mixing coagulant with water is dependent on the rate of formation of compounds capable of destabilizing the particles of pollution. An ineffective mixing moment leads to an overuse of the coagulant and a low rate of aggregation of particles at this dose of coagulant (2).

According to Abramovich G.N. mixing is "creation of a state of activity, such as flow or turbulence, in systems not in conditions of perfect mixing". The intensity of mixing is important because of increasing demands on drinking water quality. According to the data of domestic and foreign researchers, it is known that by regional process mixing reagents with water. as well as the correct choice of coagulant and flocculant,

their location and conditions for introduction into treated water can in many cases increase the performance of treatment plants, save reagents and improve the quality of the treated water (3).

The development and deepening of research on various aspects of water treatment with coagulants in mechanical mixers was reflected in the works of Pechnikov V.G., Kozlova V.I.I., Haylova E.G., Veycerov J.I. Apslzhov.E.Y and foreign authors KempaTat.PRA., Khadson.HE., Teresman.DR.

Results obtained. The adsorption of polymers on the surface of colloids is estimated in time as 10 s. Adsorption of intermediate short-lived compounds causes destabilization of the colloids and leads to agglomeration of particles.

The degree of destabilization, or efficiency of collisions, depends on the type of adsorbed compounds.

The rate of change in total particle concentration over time during ortho-kinetic flocculation can be expressed by the following equation:

$$J_{ок} = - \frac{2\eta G d_0^3 (N_0)^2}{3} \quad (1.1)$$

where: - total particle concentration in the suspension at time;

η - coefficient of impact efficiency; K - Permanent Bortsmanna; T is the absolute temperature; μ - viscosity of the liquid; d_0 - диаметр коллоидной частицы; G - the gradient of speed; $J_{нк}$ - the rate of change in total particle concentration over time during pericinetetic coagulation;

N_0 is the total particle concentration in the suspension at time (t).

The rate of change in total particle concentration over time during kinetic flocculation can be expressed by the following equation:

$$J_{нк} = - \frac{4\eta K T}{3\mu} (N_0)^2 \quad (1.2)$$

Interesting to get the ratio of the change in concentration rate by

the orthotkinetic coagulation of formula (1.1) to the concentration change rate due to the pericinetetic coagulation of formula (1.2) for any given system

$$\frac{J_{ок}}{J_{нк}} = \frac{\mu \cdot G d_0^3}{2 K T} \quad (1.3)$$

For water with a temperature of 25 0C C and the size of colloidal particles of order I in it, this ratio is one if the gradient of speed is 10c-1. It is obvious that for colloid particles of 0.1 μ m diameter, the speed gradient should be maintained at the level.

10,000 c- so that the orthokinetic coagulation is as fast as the pericinetetic one. Similarly, the orthotkinetic coagulation of particles with a diameter of 10 μ m will occur at the same speed as the impact due to diffusion, at a velocity gradient of 0.01 s⁻¹. until they are about 1 micron larger. Further growth of particles from 1 micron

requires the implementation of mixing. Therefore, it becomes obvious that when large particles are formed, the main thing is the optokinetic displacement due to the gradient of speed.

The Jar-test and production testing program was carried out in the spring of 1971. Data collected from these experiments allowed to reduce the consumption of sulphuric aluminium at the plant by about 15% and to reduce the average water turbidity after the tanks by 3035% and provided information for the development of a cost-effective project for a new water supply plant in

.Phoenix (Arizona) with a capacity of 35.00 l/s. It was determined that by improving the mixing technology, energy consumption for fast-acting mixers can be reduced. In "The Works of Walter Dag. D, dedicated to the study of the mixing nature in flocculation units with increased energy input, shows the flow regime and the system of main circulation vectors in a mechanical mixer with a turbine mixer. The painted flows formed when the liquid is injected through a small nozzle of soluble paint, gave a beautiful picture of flow structure. On rice. 2 is a system of the main circulation vectors at different circular speeds of the turbine type mixing device. The tested device was a mixer with an outside diameter of 127 cm with a hub diameter of 51 cm, installed on a vertical shaft at a depth of 1,5 m and equipped with guides - blades 61 cm wide. The tests were conducted in a range of rotational speeds of 14-60 rpm, which was consistent with the gradient of 30-110 s⁻¹.

Before this series of comparative tests, an axial inducer with an outer diameter of 152.5 cm was also tested at a speed of up to 80 umbs/min, giving (G) values up to 150 c-1. This device was the basis for creating a mixing system in the described installation.

The flow emitted by the stirrer in the modes studied was directed vertically upwards, bending halfway to the liquid mirror and transiting in a pure radial current parallel to the surface. This radial current is maintained from below by upwelling of the secondary viscous flow rising directly from the column of fluid sucked into the mixer. On the surface of the liquid above the mixer, even at the highest tested power inputs, only very little pulsation or disturbance was observed.

In his experiments with sulphuric iron without adding clay particles, Camp used a microscope to determine the number of particles, showed that during intensive stirring the bulk content of flakes is strongly dependent on the gradient of speed. After stirring for 5 min. with constant gradient of speed, the bulk content of flakes at $G = 80$ c-1 was about 350mg/l; but at $G = 1000$ c-1 volumecontent of the flakes was only 70 mg/l. The relative humidity of the flakes formed at these values of the velocity gradient was 96.5 and 89.2%, respectively.

Lagvenkar, Gemel et al. using the same coagulant, found that

the relationship between the size of the flakes formed and their density is not

is traced by intensive shuffling at values of $G = 60$ c" and below.

However, the latest study found that when increased

The intensity of mixing is a significant reduction in the size of the largest flakes. It should be noted that the high-intensity fast mixing $G > 80$ c-1 results in the rapid formation of relatively small but dense flakes.

Fig. 2 System of the main circulation vectors:

1 - electric motor; 2 - strong rotation; 3 - Liquid mirror;

4 - мешалка лопастного типа, $N=17$ об/ми., $G = 45$ c-1.

Conclusions. Thus, this mode of operation should be ensured

The coagulation agent would be involved in the hydrolysis and polymerization reaction.

However, intensive mixing can lead to coagulation overrun and low particle aggregation rate at this dose of the coagulant.

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